

1 **Designing active mats based on cellulose acetate/polycaprolactone**
2 **core/shell structures with different release kinetics**

3

4 Adrián Rojas, Eliezer Velásquez, Constanza Piña, María José Galotto, Carol López de
5 Dicastillo*

6 Packaging Innovation Center (LABEN), Department of Food Science and Technology,
7 Technology Faculty, University of Santiago de Chile (USACH), 9170201 Santiago, Chile.
8 CEDENNA (Center for the Development of Nanoscience and Nanotechnology), 9170124
9 Santiago, Chile

10 * Corresponding author: analopez.dediscastillo@usach.cl (C. López de Dicastillo)

11 E-mail addresses: adrian.rojass@usach.cl (A. Rojas), eliezer.velasquez@usach.cl (E.
12 Velásquez), constanza.pina@usach.cl (C. Piña); maria.galotto@usach.cl (M.J. Galotto)

13

14 **ABSTRACT**

15 Core/shell electrospun mats based on cellulose acetate (CA) and polycaprolactone (PCL)
16 were developed as novel active materials for releasing quercetin (Quer) and curcumin (Cur).
17 The effect of polymeric uniaxial and coaxial electrospun systems and the chemical structures
18 of Quer and Cur on the structural, thermal, and mass transference properties of the developed
19 mats were investigated. Release modelling evidenced that diffusion of the active agents from
20 the uniaxial PCL fibers was highly dependent on the type of food simulant. Higher diffusion
21 coefficients were obtained for both active agents into acid food simulant due to the higher

22 swelling of the electrospun mats. On the other hand, CA/PCL coaxial structures slowed down
23 the diffusion of both active agents into both food simulants. CA increased the active
24 compounds' affinity towards the polymer structure, resulting in partition coefficients values
25 higher than the values obtained for uniaxial active PCL mats.

26

27 **Keywords:** electrospinning, cellulose acetate, core/shell structure, kinetic release

28

29

30 **1. Introduction**

31 In the last years, the interest in designing new polymeric structures for the controlled
32 release of active agents (AA) has spread out in different areas of food science as nutraceutical
33 delivery and active food packaging applications (Guo et al., 2018; Kouhi et al., 2020). The
34 concept of controlled release packaging has recently taken great relevance with emphasis on
35 the depth understanding of the release kinetic of active agents from food packaging (X. Chen
36 et al., 2019; Yam & Zhu, 2012) . Specifically, the kinetic release of an active compound must
37 match with the food deterioration kinetics. Changes in polymer chain mobility, such as those
38 produced by plasticizers or cross-linking agents, and modifications on the diffusion path
39 length using nanofillers are the most common strategies used currently to modulate the
40 kinetic release of active compounds from polymers (Almasi et al., 2020). Nevertheless, a
41 recent trend to modify the release rate of an AA from a polymer matrix is through the
42 development of bilayer structures (Muller et al., 2017; Nilsuwan et al., 2020). In the last
43 years, coaxial electrospinning has arisen as a simple, efficient, cost-effective, and scalable
44 technology capable of producing concentric bilayer (core/shell) fibrillary structures to control
45 the release of AA due to the presence of a polymeric shell acting as a barrier layer (Li et al.,

46 2020; Rojas et al., 2020). A typical electrospinning system consists of a high-voltage power
47 supply, a syringe pump connected to a metal needle and a grounded collector. The active
48 fibrillary structures are obtained when a voltage is applied to a polymeric solution obtaining
49 a jet with a conical shape. The solvent is evaporated during the stretching and ultrafine
50 structures are deposited on the collector, which are randomly oriented nonwoven fibers with
51 diameters ranging from nanometers to micrometers and a high surface/volume ratio (Alonso-
52 González et al., 2020; Alvarado et al., 2018). Furthermore, core/shell structures can be
53 obtained through the coaxial system by using polymers with different hydrophilicity and
54 properties (Khalf et al., 2015).

55 In this work, the main objective was developing active mats based on cellulose acetate
56 and achieving different release kinetics of active compounds with antimicrobial and
57 antioxidant activities by considering that mass transfer properties are highly dependent on
58 the different chemical structures and functional groups of the AA and the structural properties
59 of developed uniaxial and core/shell electrospun fibers. Quercetin (Quer) and Curcumin
60 (Cur) were used as model agents due to their applications in active food packaging and their
61 different chemical structures (López de Dicastillo et al., 2010; Roy & Rhim, 2020). Coaxial
62 structures were designed by using polycaprolactone (PCL) and cellulose acetate (CA) for the
63 shell and core structures, respectively. PCL is an aliphatic polyester mainly used in
64 biomedical and pharmaceutical applications, but has been recently proposed for food
65 packaging applications due to its biodegradability nature and its good barrier properties due
66 to its semi-crystalline character (Zou et al., 2020). On the other hand, CA is one of the most
67 promising cellulose derivatives materials for food packaging thanks to its biodegradable
68 character, good optical properties and high toughness (Rajeswari et al., 2020; Rodríguez et
69 al., 2014). CA-based electrospun mats have been already developed principally for drug

70 carrier purposes (Y. Chen et al., 2020; Y. Yang et al., 2019) . To our knowledge, this is the
71 first study on the design of active coaxial electrospun structures based on CA loaded with
72 quercetin and curcumin and the assessment of their kinetic release to be applied in food
73 packaging.

74

75 **2. Materials and Chemicals**

76 *2.1. Materials*

77

78 Polycaprolactone (PCL) ($\overline{M}_n = 80.000$), cellulose acetate (CA) ($\overline{M}_n \sim 30.000$), quercetin
79 (Quer) ($\geq 99.5\%$) and curcumin (Cur) ($>65\%$) were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich®
80 Chemistry (Santiago, Chile). Chloroform, acetone, ethanol and N,N-dimethylformamide
81 (DMF) were supplied by Merck (Santiago, Chile).

82

83 *2.2. Development of active uniaxial and coaxial electrospun fibers*

84

85 Active core/shell structures CA-Cur/PCL and CA-Quer/PCL were processed through
86 coaxial electrospinning, and active uniaxial fibers based on PCL were also obtained, PCL-
87 Cur and PCL-Quer, in order to study the effect of both polymeric structures in the properties
88 and release of both active compounds. Additionally, control mats without active substances
89 were also prepared: PCL and CA.

90

91 *2.2.1. Preparation of polymeric solutions for electrospinning process*

92 In the case of coaxial mats, PCL solutions were prepared at 14% (w/v) under
93 chloroform/DMF (ratio 70/30) and CA solution at 17% (w/v) under acetone/water (ratio
94 85/15). Natural compounds Quer and Cur were also incorporated at CA solution at 3.35 wt%
95 respect to CA polymer weight. Control solutions for uniaxial active mats (PCL-Cur and PCL-
96 Quer) were obtained using a PCL solution at 14% (w/v) and active compounds at 1.27 wt%
97 with respect to the total polymer weight.

98

99 2.2.2. *Electrospinning process*

100 Electrospinning was carried out using an electrospinning equipment (Spraybase®power
101 SupplyUnit, Maynooth, Ireland) with a standard vertical configuration equipped with two
102 pumps, a high-voltage power and a collector plate covered with aluminum foil connected to
103 the grounded counter electrode of the power supply. A coaxial device containing two
104 concentric stainless-steel needles (0.7 mm/2.1 mm diameters) was used to process and obtain
105 active core/shell structures CA-Cur/PCL and CA-Quer/PCL and control fiber CA/PCL. Each
106 polymeric solution was introduced in a 5 mL syringe and injection flow rate used were 0.2
107 mL h⁻¹ and 0.4 mL h⁻¹ for core and shell structures, respectively. The distance between the
108 coaxial needle and collector plate was 14 cm and the applied voltage was between 11~12 kV.
109 The electrospinning process was performed for 4 h in order to obtain electrospun mats with
110 0.25~0.3 mm of thickness.

111 On the other hand, uniaxial electrospun mats PCL, PCL-Cur and PCL-Quer were
112 processed by using a single needle (0.9 mm diameter) located at 14 cm from the collector
113 plate, a flow rate of 0.4 mL h⁻¹ and a voltage between 6~7 kV. Uniaxial processes were
114 performed for 5 h, resulting in the formation of a membrane with a thickness of 0.23~0.3
115 mm. All mats were immediately removed from the aluminum foil to prevent the sample

116 from sticking and kept at 0% RH desiccators for further analysis. Uniaxial CA fibers were
117 also obtained using a flow of 2 mL h⁻¹, a distance between the capillary and the collecting
118 plate of 8 cm and a voltage between 9 and 13 kV.

119

120 *2.3. Characterization of electrospun fibers*

121

122 *2.3.1. Morphological Analysis (SEM)*

123 The morphology of the active electrospun mats were studied using a scanning electron
124 microscope (SEM) JSM-5410 Jeol with accelerating voltage at 10 kV. Samples were coated
125 with gold palladium using a Sputtering System Hummer 6.2. Average fiber diameters were
126 analyzed with image analyzer software (Image J v1.37).

127

128 *2.3.2. Structural Analysis*

129 Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) - Attenuated Total Reflectance (ATR) spectroscopy
130 was used to identify the specific functional chemical groups in the fibers. FTIR spectra were
131 performed through spectrometer equipment in ATR mode with a Bruker IFS 66V
132 spectrometer. The spectra were the result of 64 co-added interferograms at 4 cm⁻¹ and
133 resolutions in the wavenumber range from 4000 to 400 cm⁻¹. The spectra analyses were
134 performed using OPUS Software Version 7.

135

136 *2.3.3. Thermal Properties*

137 Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) analyses were performed in a Mettler Toledo
138 DSC-822e calorimeter (Mettler Toledo, Schwerzenbach, Switzerland). 5-7 mg of the samples
139 were heated from 0 to 250 °C at a constant heating rate of 10 °C.min⁻¹ under a nitrogen

140 atmosphere. The glass transition (T_g) and melting (T_m) temperatures, as well as melting
141 enthalpies (ΔH_m) were determined. The crystallinity of the fiber phases was determined by
142 $\%X_c = (\Delta H_m / \Delta H_m^0) * 100$, where ΔH_m^0 corresponds to melting heat of the 100% crystalline
143 polymer, 139.5 J g^{-1} and 58.8 J g^{-1} for PCL and CA, respectively (Cerqueira et al., 2006; Cruz
144 et al., 2019).

145 Thermogravimetric analyses (TGA) of electrospun fibers were also carried out using a
146 Mettler Toledo Gas Controller GC20 Stare System (Schwerzenbach, Switzerland)
147 TGA/DSC. Samples were heated from 30 to 600 °C at 10 °C min^{-1} under a nitrogen
148 atmosphere with a flow rate of 50 mL min^{-1} . Onset decomposition temperature (T_{onset}) at
149 $T_{2.5\%}$ and maximum degradation rate ($T_{d,\text{max}}$) were determined by the STARE software
150 (Mettler Toledo, Schwerzenbach, Switzerland).

151

152 *2.4. Release kinetic studies*

153

154 A full characterization of the mass transport process of an AA from a polymer matrix to a
155 food simulant requires the measurement of its extent and its kinetics. Therefore, Quer and
156 Cur release kinetics were characterized through specific experimental migration assays using
157 10% (v/v) ethanol (10% EtOH) and 3% (v/v) acetic acid (HAc) solutions as aqueous and
158 acidic food simulants, respectively, with the purpose to describe the mass transfer of Quer
159 and Cur from core/shell CA/PCL electrospun fibers. Migration studies were carried out
160 following the European Committee for Standardization according to EU Regulations (Rojas,
161 Velásquez, Garrido, Galotto, & López de Dicastillo, 2020; Velásquez, Rojas, Piña, Galotto,
162 & López de Dicastillo, 2019). Electrospun mats loaded with Quer or Cur were totally
163 immersed into glass tubes filled with food simulants in a relation of $6 \text{ dm}^2 \text{ L}^{-1}$. Release assays

164 were carried out at 40 °C and the amount of Quer and Cur released was periodically measured
165 by UV spectroscopy at 425 and 298 nm for Quer and Cur, respectively. Release assays were
166 performed until the equilibrium condition was reached, i.e. when released Quer and Cur was
167 maintained constant in time in at least two continuous consecutive measurements. Diffusion
168 coefficients (D) of both active compounds in the core-shell PCL/CA electrospun mats were
169 calculated following Fick's laws according to the method used in previous works (López-
170 Carballo, Cava, Lagarón, Catalá, & Gavara, 2005; López-de-Dicastillo, Alonso, Catalá,
171 Gavara, & Hernández-Muñoz, 2010; López-de-Dicastillo, Gómez-Estaca, Catalá, Gavara, &
172 Hernández-Muñoz, 2012). Partition constants ($K_{P/FS}$) of each AA into electrospun mats/food
173 simulant systems were estimated through the concentration values at equilibrium.

174 Fick's law considering boundary conditions of the experiments was applied to
175 characterize the kinetics of the mass transport process within a polymer matrix. In this work,
176 D values for the transport of AA in the core/shell electrospun mats were considered
177 independent of time and position. Moreover, these release process conditions were: (1) AA
178 were released by both sides of the core/shell electrospun mats; (2) the initial AA
179 concentration in the electrospun mat was known and homogeneously distributed; (3) the food
180 simulant was initially AA-free; (4) the extent of the release was controlled by an equilibrium
181 which can be represented by the partition coefficient ($K_{P/FS}$) calculated as the ratio between
182 the concentration of the AA in the polymeric electrospun mat (C_P) and in the food simulant
183 (C_{FS}) at equilibrium time: $K_{P/FS}=C_P/C_{FS}$; and (5) the food simulant medium is finite and the
184 concentration of the AA is homogeneous. Thus, the ratio of the AA released mass into the
185 simulant over time can be expressed as:

186
$$\frac{m(t)}{m_s^f} = \left[1 - \frac{8}{\pi^2} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n+1)^2} \exp\left(\frac{-D(2n+1)^2\pi^2 t}{l^2}\right) \right] \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

187

188 2.5. Statistical analysis

189

190 A random-type experimental design was used. Data analysis was carried out using
191 Statgraphics Plus 5.1. This software was used to implement variance analysis and Fisher's
192 LSD test. Differences were considered significant at $p < 0.05$.

193

194 3. Results and discussion

195 All active fibers presented a final concentration of 1.25 wt% of AA with respect to the
196 total polymer(s) weight. Table 1 exhibits the composition of all developed uniaxial and
197 coaxial fibers.

198

199 **Table 1**

200 Composition of developed electrospun mats.

Uniaxial fibers	PCL (wt%)	CA (wt%)	AA (wt%)
PCL-Cur	98.75	-	1.25
PCL-Quer	98.75	-	1.25
PCL	100	-	-
CA	-	100	-
Core/shell fibers	PCL (wt%)	CA (wt%)	AA (wt%)
CA-Cur/PCL	61.44	37.31	1.25
CA-Quer/PCL	61.44	37.31	1.25
CA/PCL	62.22	37.78	-

201

202 3.1. Morphological and structural characterization

203 SEM micrographs, fiber average diameter and fiber diameter distribution of the active
204 electrospun mats are depicted in Fig. 1.

205

206

207 **Fig. 1.** SEM micrographs at 5 and 15 kx and the fiber diameter distribution of active
208 electrospun mats: (a) PCL-Cur; (b) CA-Cur/PCL; (c) PCL-Quer; and (d) CA-Quer/PCL.

209

210 Uniaxial (PCL-Cur and PCL-Quer) and core/shell (CA-Cur/PCL and CA-Quer/PCL)
211 polymeric solutions rendered continuous fibers without beads and with similar average fiber
212 diameters. Uniaxial PCL fibers containing Cur (Fig. 1a) and Quer (Fig.1c) presented some
213 agglomeration and attachment, possibly due to the AA's presence on polymer surface

214 promoted fiber-fiber interactions, or slower evaporation of the solvent mixture used for PCL
215 uniaxial electrospinning caused fiber stacking. On the contrary, this phenomenon was almost
216 indiscernible for core/shell fibers, where the active compound was encapsulated into the CA
217 core, resulting CA-Cur/PCL the coaxial fiber with the narrower diameter distribution.

218 In general, the average diameter of the fibers were similar. Although the needle diameter
219 used for coaxial structures was larger, the use of a higher voltage in this process induced
220 stronger polymeric stretching that resulted in fibers with similar diameters than uniaxial
221 fibers obtained by conventional electrospinning process.

222 The FTIR spectra of active PCL uniaxial mats and PCL control mats presented a similar
223 profile (Fig. 2). The major absorption band due to the stretching of carbonyl from the ester
224 groups was observed at 1730 cm^{-1} . Characteristic peaks in PCL-based mats appeared at 2942
225 and 2866 cm^{-1} related to asymmetric and symmetric stretching vibrations of methylene
226 groups, respectively.

227

228

229 **Fig. 2.** Spectra FTIR of active PCL uniaxial and control mats.

230

231 Bands at 1471 and 1363 cm^{-1} belonged to symmetric deformation and symmetric wagging
232 of CH_2 , respectively. Other peaks appeared at 1295, 1242, 1162 and 1042 cm^{-1} corresponding
233 to C-O and C-C stretching, asymmetric C-O-C stretching, symmetric C-O-C stretching, C-O
234 stretching and C-H bending, respectively. In addition, peaks at 961 and 731 cm^{-1} were
235 associated with C-C stretching (Awasthi et al., 2020; Srikanth et al., 2019). Besides, some
236 peaks of Cur and Quer could be overlapped by PCL bands and unique characteristic peaks of
237 flavonoids did not appear due to their low concentrations. These peaks were related to i)
238 benzene ring at 1625 cm^{-1} and C=C vibrations at 1506 cm^{-1} for curcumin and ii) C=O aryl
239 ketone groups and C=C aromatic ring vibrations between 1666 and 1510 cm^{-1} for quercetin
240 (Catauro et al., 2015; Tsekova et al., 2017). However, PCL major absorption band at 1730
241 cm^{-1} slightly shifted to 1720 cm^{-1} in the uniaxial active mats. The displacement can be
242 attributed to hydrogen bonding between hydroxyl groups of the flavonoids and PCL carbonyl
243 groups. On the other hand, CA fibers presented clear peaks at 1730 cm^{-1} associated to
244 stretching of C=O groups, 1364 cm^{-1} to C-H bending of methylene groups, and 1212 and
245 1030 cm^{-1} corresponding to stretching vibration of C-O-C linkage of the backbone, as shown
246 in Fig. 3 (Khalf et al., 2015). Interestingly, in active coaxial mats, several characteristic bands
247 from both PCL and CA were observed and displacement of their peaks occurred due to
248 chemical interactions between core/shell polymers and flavonoids.

249 The most displaced peaks in the coaxial mats spectra with respect to control polymers
250 were exhibited at 1720, 1356, 1212 and 1037 cm^{-1} , regarding to carbonyl stretching, C-H
251 vibrations of methylene groups and vibrations in C-O-C groups. Besides, similarly to those
252 observed in PCL mats, flavonoid bands could be overlapped by polymer peaks or were not
253 detected because of their low concentration.

255

256

Fig. 3. FTIR spectra of active coaxial and control PCL and CA mats.

257

258 3.2. Thermal properties results

259

260 DSC parameters of uniaxial and coaxial electrospun structures are important in order to
 261 understand the differences in crystallinity which can be closely related to the release process
 262 of active materials. Thermal parameters of electrospun mats from DSC analysis are shown
 263 in Table 2, excepting data of glass transition process because, although the glass transition
 264 (T_g) of control CA fibers associated with the amorphous CA phase was recorded at 187 °C,
 265 glass transitions temperatures of active CA/PCL coaxial fibers were not detected (Hassan et
 266 al., 2019; Tsekova et al., 2017).

267

268 **Table 2**

269 DSC parameters and crystallinity of the fibers during the first heating process.

Electrospun mat	T _{m1} (°C)	T _{m2} (°C)	ΔH _{m,PCL} (J.g ⁻¹)	ΔH _{m,CA} (J.g ⁻¹)	X _{c,PCL} ^a (%)	X _{c,CA} ^a (%)
PCL	59.2 ± 0.8 ^a		108.7 ± 1.1 ^c	-	77.9 ± 0.8 ^c	-
CA	-	227.0 ± 1.2 ^a	-	13.4 ± 0.2 ^b	-	22.8 ± 0.4 ^b
PCL-Cur	59.9 ± 3.0 ^a		109.3 ± 4.7 ^c	-	78.3 ± 3.4 ^c	-
PCL-Quer	61.4 ± 2.0 ^a		85.6 ± 0.3 ^b	-	61.4 ± 0.2 ^b	-
CA-Cur/PCL	60.8 ± 1.8 ^a	224.9 ± 1.2 ^a	55.9 ± 5.5 ^a	3.4 ± 0.1 ^a	40.1 ± 4.0 ^a	5.7 ± 0.2 ^a
CA-Quer/PCL	62.1 ± 0.1 ^a	225.7 ± 1.9 ^a	56.4 ± 2.7 ^a	4.1 ± 0.3 ^a	40.5 ± 2.0 ^a	7.0 ± 0.6 ^a

270 Letters a-c superscript letters indicate statistical differences of the parameters among samples
 271 according to ANOVA analysis and Fisher LSD test. Mean value and standard deviation correspond
 272 to two replicates for each sample. The crystallinity of the phases presented in each fiber was
 273 calculated respect to the melting heat of the corresponding 100% crystalline polymer.

274

275 During the first heating process, active coaxial mats revealed two melting processes at T_{m1}
 276 and T_{m2} temperatures, associated with the melting transitions of the crystalline phases of PCL
 277 and CA, respectively. These temperatures were similar to the melting process of each control
 278 PCL and CA mats (Table 2). Nevertheless, melting enthalpies of PCL and CA crystalline
 279 phases in the active coaxial fibers were lower than the corresponding enthalpies of control
 280 uniaxial fibers. Therefore, polymeric phases in the active coaxial fibers were less crystalline.
 281 The reduction of crystallinity can be attributed to the restriction of the mobility of the polymer
 282 chains during the formation of the fibers, due to polymer-polymer and polymer-active agent
 283 interactions, which hindered rearrangement and crystallization. These chemical interactions
 284 were also observed through peak FTIR spectra displacements, and they can be: i) hydrogen
 285 bonds principally between PCL carbonyl groups in the shell and the hydroxyl groups of the
 286 CA, Cur or Quer in the core-shell interphase; and ii) hydrogen bonding interactions between

287 the functional groups (carbonyls, hydroxyls or ether groups) of the CA and Cur or Quer in
288 the core. Similarly, hydrogen bonding type interactions have been already reported between
289 CA and PCL/chitosan groups (Wang et al., 2017), CA and Cur in solid dispersions (Wan et
290 al., 2012a), PCL and Quer in copolymer micelles (X. Yang et al., 2008) and CA and Quer in
291 CA-polyethylene glycol active fibers (Stoyanova et al., 2020). This reduction of PCL and
292 CA crystallinities in both active coaxial mats were statistically similar for both phenolic
293 compounds. Furthermore, the melting transition of Cur at 176 °C was undetectable, possibly
294 due to its low concentration in the active fibers. The upper-temperature limit used for the
295 heating process was below the melting temperature of Quer at 323 °C (Stoyanova et al.,
296 2020).

297 Additionally, the thermal parameters of the PCL uniaxial fibers containing Cur or Quer
298 were analyzed and the interactions between AA and PCL groups were verified. The melting
299 process peak of PCL from both active and control uniaxial fibers occurred at 60 °C approx.,
300 and PCL-Quer mat registered the lowest crystallinity value. This fact may be due to a greater
301 hydrogen bonding interaction, principally between the PCL carbonyl groups and the
302 functional groups of Quer, whose structure owns a higher number of hydroxyl groups. The
303 rigidity of the quercetin molecule and its most significant interaction with the PCL inhibited
304 the mobility of polymer chains, reducing its ability to reorder and crystallize during the
305 electrospinning process. The effect of this phenomenon on the glass transition associated
306 with the amorphous regions of the PCL fibers was not detected because PCL glass transition
307 has been reported around -60 °C and the thermal range used during the first heating process
308 began at 0 °C (Bassi et al., 2011).

309 The onset decomposition temperature and the temperature at the maximum degradation
310 rate of the fibers and the active compounds are shown in Table 3 and Fig. 4.

311

312 **Table 3**

313 TGA parameters of the fibers and antioxidant agents.

Electrospun mat	T_{onset} (°C)	T_{d,max1} (°C)	T_{d,max2} (°C)
Cur	267.3	305.4	391.6
Quer	117	124	354.9
CA	276.3	361.6	-
PCL	388.7	412.7	-
PCL-Cur	356.4	413.9	-
PCL-Quer	369.9	408.6	-
CA-Cur/PCL	309.7	355.8	409.8
CA-Quer/PCL	294.8	356.7	411.4

314 T_{onset} is the temperature at 2.5% of weight loss.315 T_{d,max1} and T_{d,max2} are the temperatures at the maximum degradation rates.

316

317 The maximum degradation of CA mat occurred at 361.6 °C by decomposition of
318 glycosidic linkages, depolymerization, dehydration and loss of acetate groups (Cheng et al.,
319 2017). PCL degradation occurred in a single step at 412.7 °C (Fig. 4a) through the generation
320 of small molecules such as H₂O, CO₂ and 5-hexenoic acid by random cleavage of the
321 polyester chain and ε-caprolactone by unzipping depolymerization process (Persenaire et al.,
322 2001). The maximum degradation rate of both active coaxial fibers occurred at similar
323 temperatures, and as Fig. 4a, b show, two degradation stages were observed corresponding
324 to CA (T_{d,max1}) and PCL (T_{d,max2}) phases. Furthermore, the presence of CA accelerated the
325 onset decomposition of coaxial fibers compared to uniaxial active PCL mats, although the
326 decomposition of CA-Quer/PCL mat started at a lower temperature (Table 3), probably
327 because the anhydrous quercetin presented an earlier first decomposition stage at a lower
328 temperature (124 °C) than the Cur (305.4 °C) (Rojas et al., 2020; Velásquez et al., 2019).

329

330
 331 **Fig. 4.** DTGA curves of: (a) components and (b) active electrospun mats.
 332

333 On the other hand, active uniaxial fibers were more thermally stable than the
 334 corresponding coaxial fibers containing each active agent. This fact could be due to a greater
 335 interaction between the functional groups of both polyphenolic compounds with PCL
 336 functional groups than with CA chemical groups.

337 As DSC analysis evidenced, the lower rigidity of the PCL chains ($T_g = -60$ °C) compared
 338 to CA ($T_g = 187$ °C) favored their mobility and PCL-active agent interactions, forming a
 339 more stable structure (Vidéki et al., 2007). Besides, the higher onset decomposition

340 temperature of the PCL-Quer fiber compared to the PCL-Cur mat could confirm a more
341 stable structure in the first case because of the greater number of functional groups in the
342 Quer. These chemical groups were available to create hydrogen bonding interactions with
343 PCL carbonyl groups mainly, in agreement with the DSC analysis.

344

345 *3.4 Study of the release kinetics of quercetin and curcumin from CA/PCL core/shell* 346 *electrospun fibers*

347

348 Release kinetics of Quer and Cur from developed electrospun mats immersed into 10%
349 EtOH and 3% HAc, expressed as mass of AA (mg) per volume (mL) of food simulant are
350 shown in Fig. 5. The graphs represent experimental and theoretical description obtained using
351 equation (1). The equilibrium condition was expressed in terms of the partition coefficient
352 of the active compounds ($K_{P/FS}$) which is a thermodynamic parameter that corresponds to the
353 ratio between the concentration of the AA in the polymer (P) and the food simulant (FS).
354 Meanwhile, the kinetic process was defined in terms of the diffusion coefficient (D) of the
355 AA inside the polymeric matrix (López de Dicastillo et al., 2010; López de Dicastillo et al.,
356 2011; López de Dicastillo et al., 2012).

357 As shown by release kinetic curves in Fig. 5, theoretical curves highly fitted with the
358 experimental data. This fact evidenced that Quer and Cur release from uniaxial PCL-Quer
359 and PCL-Cur mats and core/shell CA-Quer/PCL and CA-Cur/PCL fibers were mainly
360 controlled by the diffusion phenomenon in the polymer structure defined by Fick's law. The
361 curve slope of the kinetics of Quer and Cur concentration values in the food simulant greatly
362 depended on the mat structure (uniaxial or core/shell) and the food simulant.

363

364

365 **Fig. 5.** Release kinetics of Quer and Cur from CA/PCL core/shell electrospun fibers and
 366 uniaxial PCL fibers into: a) 10% EtOH; and b) 3% HAc. Symbols represent experimental
 367 data, and lines are values predicted using eq (1).

368

369 Table 4 presents the diffusion coefficients values of Quer and Cur through uniaxial and
 370 core/shell fibers in both simulants. *D* values of uniaxial fibers were dependent on the type of
 371 the food simulant used. Into 10% EtOH, *D* values for Quer ($6.5 \times 10^{-15} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$) and Cur (8.0

372 $\times 10^{-15} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$) from uniaxial PCL fibers were similar. Nevertheless, differences between both
 373 active PCL mats into acidic simulants were more pronounced.

374

375 **Table 4**

376 $K_{P/FS}$ and D values of Quer and Cur from uniaxial and core/shell electrospun materials into
 377 different food simulants at 40 °C.

Active agent	Food Simulant	Electrospun mat	$K_{P/FS}$	D_P ($\text{m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$)
Quer	10% EtOH	PCL-Quer	10767 ± 105	6.50E-15
		CA-Quer/PCL	23649 ± 220	2.50E-15
	3% HAc	PCL-Quer	4184 ± 100	3.00E-13
		CA-Quer/PCL	5833 ± 98	1.20E-14
Cur	10% EtOH	PCL-Cur	16228 ± 89	8.00E-15
		CA-Cur/PCL	16413 ± 40	2.50E-15
	3% HAc	PCL-Cur	14088 ± 100	3.00E-14
		CA-Cur/PCL	14441 ± 78	1.50E-14

378

379 The differences between food simulants can be mainly explained by the PCL swelling and
 380 plasticization due to the penetration of food simulant inside the polymer. This phenomenon
 381 modified the effective transport properties of PCL during the release assay improving the
 382 mass transfer of Quer and Cur, involving in the overestimation of their values of D in the
 383 polymer matrix. Thus, in acidic simulants, swelling degrees were greatly increased for both
 384 active uniaxial PCL fibers. Furthermore, the polymeric swelling is highly dependent on its
 385 crystallinity degree. In this context, the crystallinity degree of PCL-Quer fiber (61.4%) was
 386 lower than the PCL-Cur (78.3%). This fact could be related to a higher degree of swelling
 387 for PCL-Quer fiber than for PCL-Cur fiber during release assays done in acidic media, which

388 drastically improved the release kinetic of Quer through the polymer structure. On the other
389 hand, when compared to other active polymers, D value for Cur in the uniaxial PCL-based
390 fibers into 10% EtOH was 44-fold lower than reported D value for Cur in uniaxial PLA-
391 based fibers ($3.5 \times 10^{-13} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$) (Rojas et al., 2020). This result was expected because PCL-
392 Cur fiber presented higher crystallinity degree (78.3%) than PLA-Cur fibers (6.2%), which
393 hindered the diffusion of Cur through the electrospun PCL fiber. Meanwhile, D value of Quer
394 in electrospun fibers were not previously reported according to our knowledge.

395 On the other hand, as it was expected, D values of core/shell mats CA-Quer/PCL and CA-
396 Cur/PCL were lower than values of uniaxial mats. This decrease occurred because both active
397 components were distributed into the CA inner layer of core/shell structures. Thus, Quer and
398 Cur must diffuse through the entire PCL shell-layer before being released into the food
399 simulant. On the contrary, in the case of uniaxial fibers, active compounds only diffuse
400 through the porous PCL structure. Interestingly, when both active core/shell mats containing
401 Quer and Cur were compared, D values were similar for every food simulant. The outer PCL
402 layer similarly acted in both active core/shell mats and hindered in the same extent the
403 diffusion phenomenon of Quer and Cur. This fact agrees with the same crystallinity degree
404 for PCL phases of both coaxial fibers, which is certainly the main physical property that
405 governs the solute mass transfer inside a polymer (Table 2). Regarding the effect of food
406 simulant, as occurred for uniaxial mats, D values in acidic media were higher than diffusion
407 processes into 10% EtOH due to higher swelling degree in this media.

408 As Table 4 shows, $K_{P/FS}$ values of Quer and Cur from uniaxial (PCL-Quer and PCL-Cur)
409 and core/shell (CA-Quer/PCL and CA-Cur/PCL) mats into 10% EtOH and 3% HAc were
410 dependent on food simulant. In both media, the $K_{P/FS}$ values for Quer released from uniaxial
411 PCL-Quer fiber were lower than $K_{P/FS}$ value of Cur released from uniaxial PCL-Cur fibers,

412 showing that Quer presented a higher tendency to migrate (see Fig. 5). Because electrospun
413 samples presented the same initial concentration of both AA (1.25 wt%), the differences
414 between $K_{P/FS}$ values in the uniaxial fibers was a consequence of the different chemical
415 affinities between the AA and the food simulant solutions. A thermodynamic parameter
416 related to the chemical affinity between a solute and a solvent correspond to solubility, being
417 hydrogen bond the most powerful intermolecular interaction that contributes to increase the
418 solubility of neutral (uncharged) molecules in a liquid. In this context, the higher tendency
419 experimented for Quer to migrate could be related to its higher capacity to interact with these
420 solutions by hydrogen bonding. Quer presents a higher number of hydrogen bond donor
421 moieties ($n=5$) than Cur chemical structure ($n=2$). In fact, the lowest $K_{P/FS}$ value occurred
422 into the acidic media probably due to the highest presence of hydrogen bond acceptors
423 moieties.

424 Regarding active electrospun mats containing Quer, $K_{P/FS}$ values of core/shell structure
425 (CA-Quer/PCL) were lower than uniaxial structure (PCL-Quer). This tendency was observed
426 for both food simulants. The increase of $K_{P/FS}$ between coaxial and uniaxial mats into 10%
427 EtOH (2.19-fold) was higher than the increase of $K_{P/FS}$ obtained into 3% HAc (1.39-fold).
428 This fact can be explained in terms of the higher swelling of the CA-Quer/PCL fibers when
429 they were exposed to acidic media. The swelling of a polymer system into solvents involves
430 the penetration of solvent inside the polymer structure which affected negatively the chemical
431 interactions between AA and the polymer matrix, and therefore contributed to a higher
432 release of the AA to the food simulant. The effect of core-shell structure on the increase of
433 $K_{P/FS}$ value must be a consequence of the establishment of a higher affinity between Quer and
434 the polymer structure. Thus, the presence of Quer into a thin inner CA fiber increased the
435 affinity of Quer to the polymeric phase decreasing the total amount of Quer released to the

436 food simulant. The increase of the cohesive energy between Cur and the CA polymer phase
437 could be explained due to a greater chemical interaction between this AA and CA.
438 Specifically, oxygen atom from CA hydroxyl groups are better hydrogen bond acceptors than
439 the oxygen atom of PCL carbonyl groups (De Vries & Smit, 1969).

440 Regarding active electrospun mats containing Cur, $K_{P/FS}$ for coaxial mats were slightly
441 higher than PCL-Cur uniaxial fibers into both food simulants (see Fig. 5b). This result was
442 unexpected because affinity between Cur and CA by means of hydrogen bonding is well-
443 known (Tsekova et al., 2017; Wan et al., 2012b), and therefore, a higher difference between
444 $K_{P/FS}$ values obtained for uniaxial and core-shell mats was expected. In this context, the
445 saturation with Cur into the food simulants could have occurred, a phenomenon that limited
446 the Cur release. Although any previous data regarding the maximum solubility of curcumin
447 into these food simulants have been reported, as a reference point, the extremely low
448 solubility value of curcumin in water (11 ng L^{-1}) is known. In this research, higher
449 concentrations values for Cur in the equilibrium time due to its release in 10% EtOH (0.74
450 mg L^{-1}) and in 3% HAc (0.87 mg L^{-1}) were 67 and 79-fold higher than the value of Cur
451 solubility in water, respectively.

452

453 **4. Conclusions**

454 Active biodegradable core/shell fibers based on cellulose acetate and polycaprolactone
455 (PCL), as inner and outer layers, respectively, were successfully developed by coaxial
456 electrospinning with the objective of achieving different release kinetics than common
457 uniaxial electrospun fibers. Different release kinetics were also observed by using two active
458 compounds with different chemical structures and functional groups. Curcumin and

459 quercetin presented more significant interactions with PCL than cellulose acetate. The
460 crystallinities of PCL and cellulose acetate phases in the core/shell structures containing
461 curcumin or quercetin were similar. Encapsulating these compounds in a cellulose acetate
462 core with a PCL outer layer inhibited stacking and agglomeration of the active fibers.
463 Likewise, PCL shell effectively reduced diffusion of the active agent throughout the fiber
464 which varied according to the type of food simulant. Although differences in the diffusion
465 coefficients (D) of the active agents in a specific food simulant were observed due to different
466 chemical structures, D values of core/shell structures with curcumin or quercetin were
467 interestingly similar. Finally, designing active PCL/cellulose acetate core/shell mats
468 increased partition coefficients compared to the corresponding uniaxial PCL fibers, with a
469 maximum value for coaxial fiber with quercetin in EtOH 10%, indicating a significant
470 reduction of the total compound release.

471

472 **Acknowledgments**

473 The authors acknowledge the financial support of Agencia Nacional de Investigación y
474 Desarrollo de Chile (ANID) through the Fondecyt Regular Project N° 1200766, CONICYT
475 Fondecyt Postdoctoral Grant 3190929 and the “Programa de Financiamiento Basal para
476 Centros Científicos y Tecnológicos de Excelencia” (Project AFB180001).

477

478 **Author contributions**

479 **Adrián Rojas:** Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing - Original Draft. **Eliezer**
480 **Velásquez:** Conceptualization, Data curation, Writing - Review & Editing, Visualization.

481 **Constanza Piña:** Methodology, Data analysis. **María José Galotto:** Resources,
482 Supervision. **Carol López de Dicastillo:** Project administration, Funding acquisition,
483 Writing - Review & Editing, Supervision.
484

485 **References**

486 Almasi, H., Jahanbakhsh Oskouie, M., & Saleh, A. (2020). A review on techniques utilized
487 for design of controlled release food active packaging. In *Critical Reviews in Food*
488 *Science and Nutrition*. Taylor and Francis Inc.
489 <https://doi.org/10.1080/10408398.2020.1783199>

490 Alonso-González, M., Corral-González, A., Felix, M., Romero, A., & Martin-Alfonso, J. E.
491 (2020). Developing active poly(vinyl alcohol)-based membranes with encapsulated
492 antimicrobial enzymes via electrospinning for food packaging. *International Journal of*
493 *Biological Macromolecules*, *162*, 913–921.
494 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2020.06.217>

495 Alvarado, N., Romero, J., Torres, A., López de Dicastillo, C., Rojas, A., Galotto, M. J., &
496 Guarda, A. (2018). Supercritical impregnation of thymol in poly(lactic acid) filled with
497 electrospun poly(vinyl alcohol)-cellulose nanocrystals nanofibers: Development an
498 active food packaging material. *Journal of Food Engineering*, *217*.
499 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfoodeng.2017.08.008>

500 Awasthi, G. P., Maharjan, B., Shrestha, S., Bhattarai, D. P., Yoon, D., Park, C. H., & Kim,
501 C. S. (2020). Synthesis, characterizations, and biocompatibility evaluation of
502 polycaprolactone–MXene electrospun fibers. *Colloids and Surfaces A:*

503 *Physicochemical and Engineering Aspects*, 586, 124282.
504 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.colsurfa.2019.124282>

505 Bassi, A. K., Gough, J. E., Zakikhani, M., & Downes, S. (2011). The Chemical and Physical
506 Properties of Poly(ϵ -caprolactone) Scaffolds Functionalised with Poly(vinyl
507 phosphonic acid-co-acrylic acid). *Journal of Tissue Engineering*, 2011.
508 <https://doi.org/10.4061/2011/615328>

509 Catauro, M., Papale, F., Bollino, F., Piccolella, S., Marciano, S., Nocera, P., & Pacifico, S.
510 (2015). Silica/quercetin sol-gel hybrids as antioxidant dental implant materials. *Science
511 and Technology of Advanced Materials*, 16(3). [https://doi.org/10.1088/1468-
512 6996/16/3/035001](https://doi.org/10.1088/1468-6996/16/3/035001)

513 Cerqueira, D. A., Rodrigues Filho, G., & Assunção, R. M. N. (2006). A New Value for the
514 Heat of Fusion of a Perfect Crystal of Cellulose Acetate. *Polymer Bulletin*, 56(4), 475–
515 484. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00289-006-0511-9>

516 Chen, X., Chen, M., Xu, C., & Yam, K. L. (2019). Critical review of controlled release
517 packaging to improve food safety and quality. *Critical Reviews in Food Science and
518 Nutrition*, 59(15), 2386–2399. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10408398.2018.1453778>

519 Chen, Y., Qiu, Y., Chen, W., & Wei, Q. (2020). Electrospun thymol-loaded porous cellulose
520 acetate fibers with potential biomedical applications. *Materials Science and
521 Engineering C*, 109, 110536. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.msec.2019.110536>

522 Cheng, M., Qin, Z., Hu, S., Yu, H., & Zhu, M. (2017). Use of electrospinning to directly
523 fabricate three-dimensional nanofiber stacks of cellulose acetate under high relative
524 humidity condition. *Cellulose*, 24(1), 219–229. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10570-016->

525 1099-3

526 Cruz, Y., Muñoz, E., Gomez-Pachón, E. Y., Morales-Corona, J., Olayo-Lortia, J., Olayo, R.,
527 & Olayo-Valles, R. (2019). Electrospun PCL-protein scaffolds coated by pyrrole plasma
528 polymerization. *Journal of Biomaterials Science, Polymer Edition*, 30(10), 832–845.
529 <https://doi.org/10.1080/09205063.2019.1603338>

530 De Vries, J. H., & Smit, M. J. (1969). Adsorptive properties of cellulose acetate : Part IV :
531 adsorption of aromatic alcohols, amines and dihydric phenols. *South African Journal of*
532 *Chemistry*, 22, 128–131. https://journals.co.za/content/chem/22/2/AJA03794350_1774

533 Guo, C., Yin, J., & Chen, D. (2018). Co-encapsulation of curcumin and resveratrol into novel
534 nutraceutical hyalurosomes nano-food delivery system based on oligo-hyaluronic acid-
535 curcumin polymer. *Carbohydrate Polymers*, 181, 1033–1037.
536 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbpol.2017.11.046>

537 Hassan, M., Berglund, L., Abou-Zeid, R., Hassan, E., Abou-Elseoud, W., & Oksman, K.
538 (2019). Nanocomposite film based on cellulose acetate and lignin-rich rice straw
539 nanofibers. *Materials*, 12(4). <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma12040595>

540 Khalf, A., Singarapu, K., & Madihally, S. V. (2015). Cellulose acetate core–shell structured
541 electrospun fiber: fabrication and characterization. *Cellulose*, 22(2), 1389–1400.
542 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10570-015-0555-9>

543 Kouhi, M., Prabhakaran, M. P., & Ramakrishna, S. (2020). Edible polymers: An insight into
544 its application in food, biomedicine and cosmetics. In *Trends in Food Science and*
545 *Technology* (Vol. 103, pp. 248–263). Elsevier Ltd.
546 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tifs.2020.05.025>

547 Li, Y., Dong, Q., Chen, J., & Li, L. (2020). Effects of coaxial electrospun eugenol loaded
548 core-sheath PVP/shellac fibrous films on postharvest quality and shelf life of
549 strawberries. *Postharvest Biology and Technology*, 159, 111028.
550 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.postharvbio.2019.111028>

551 López de Dicastillo, C., Alonso, J., Catalá, R., Gavara, R., & Hernández-Munoz, P. (2010).
552 Improving the antioxidant protection of packaged food by incorporating natural
553 flavonoids into ethylene-vinyl alcohol copolymer (EVOH) films. *Journal of*
554 *Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 58(20). <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf1022324>

555 López de Dicastillo, C., Gómez-Estaca, J., Catalá, R., Gavara, R., & Hernández-Muñoz, P.
556 (2012). Active antioxidant packaging films: Development and effect on lipid stability
557 of brined sardines. *Food Chemistry*, 131(4).
558 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2011.10.002>

559 López de Dicastillo, C., Nerín, C., Alfaro, P., Catalá, R., Gavara, R., & Hernández-Muñoz,
560 P. (2011). Development of New Antioxidant Active Packaging Films Based on Ethylene
561 Vinyl Alcohol Copolymer (EVOH) and Green Tea Extract. *Journal of Agricultural and*
562 *Food Chemistry*, 59(14), 7832–7840. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf201246g>

563 Muller, J., Casado Quesada, A., González-Martínez, C., & Chiralt, A. (2017). Antimicrobial
564 properties and release of cinnamaldehyde in bilayer films based on polylactic acid
565 (PLA) and starch. *European Polymer Journal*, 96, 316–325.
566 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eurpolymj.2017.09.009>

567 Niluwan, K., Guerrero, P., de la Caba, K., Benjakul, S., & Prodpran, T. (2020). Properties
568 and application of bilayer films based on poly (lactic acid) and fish gelatin containing

569 epigallocatechin gallate fabricated by thermo-compression molding. *Food*
570 *Hydrocolloids*, 105, 105792.
571 <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodhyd.2020.105792>

572 Persenaire, O., Alexandre, M., Degée, P., & Dubois, P. (2001). Mechanisms and Kinetics of
573 Thermal Degradation of Poly(ϵ -caprolactone). *Biomacromolecules*, 2(1), 288–294.
574 <https://doi.org/10.1021/bm0056310>

575 Rajeswari, A., Christy, E. J. S., Swathi, E., & Pius, A. (2020). Fabrication of improved
576 cellulose acetate-based biodegradable films for food packaging applications.
577 *Environmental Chemistry and Ecotoxicology*, 2, 107–114.
578 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eneco.2020.07.003>

579 Rodríguez, F. J., Torres, A., Peñaloza, Á., Sepúlveda, H., Galotto, M. J., Guarda, A., &
580 Bruna, J. (2014). Development of an antimicrobial material based on a nanocomposite
581 cellulose acetate film for active food packaging. *Food Additives and Contaminants -*
582 *Part A Chemistry, Analysis, Control, Exposure and Risk Assessment*, 31(3), 342–353.
583 <https://doi.org/10.1080/19440049.2013.876105>

584 Rojas, A., Velásquez, E., Garrido, L., Galotto, M. J., & López de Dicastillo, C. (2020).
585 Design of active electrospun mats with single and core-shell structures to achieve
586 different curcumin release kinetics. *Journal of Food Engineering*, 273.
587 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfoodeng.2019.109900>

588 Roy, S., & Rhim, J. W. (2020). Preparation of bioactive functional poly(lactic acid)/curcumin
589 composite film for food packaging application. *International Journal of Biological*
590 *Macromolecules*, 162, 1780–1789. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2020.08.094>

591 Srikanth, M., Asmatulu, R., Cluff, K., & Yao, L. (2019). Material Characterization and
592 Bioanalysis of Hybrid Scaffolds of Carbon Nanomaterial and Polymer Nanofibers. *ACS*
593 *Omega*, 4(3), 5044–5051. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsomega.9b00197>

594 Stoyanova, N., Spasova, M., Manolova, N., Rashkov, I., Georgieva, A., & Toshkova, R.
595 (2020). Antioxidant and antitumor activities of novel quercetin-loaded electrospun
596 cellulose acetate/polyethylene glycol fibrous materials. *Antioxidants*, 9(3).
597 <https://doi.org/10.3390/antiox9030232>

598 Tsekova, P. B., Spasova, M. G., Manolova, N. E., Markova, N. D., & Rashkov, I. B. (2017).
599 Electrospun curcumin-loaded cellulose acetate/polyvinylpyrrolidone fibrous materials
600 with complex architecture and antibacterial activity. *Materials Science and Engineering*
601 *C*, 73, 206–214. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.msec.2016.12.086>

602 Velásquez, E., Rojas, A., Piña, C., Galotto, M. J., & López de Dicastillo, C. (2019).
603 Development of bilayer biodegradable composites containing cellulose nanocrystals
604 with antioxidant properties. *Polymers*, 11(12). <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym11121945>

605 Vidéki, B., Klébert, S., & Pukánszky, B. (2007). External and internal plasticization of
606 cellulose acetate with caprolactone: Structure and properties. *Journal of Polymer*
607 *Science Part B: Polymer Physics*, 45(8), 873–883. <https://doi.org/10.1002/polb.21121>

608 Wan, S., Sun, Y., Qi, X., & Tan, F. (2012a). Improved bioavailability of poorly water-soluble
609 drug curcumin in cellulose acetate solid dispersion. *AAPS PharmSciTech*, 13(1), 159–
610 166. <https://doi.org/10.1208/s12249-011-9732-9>

611 Wan, S., Sun, Y., Qi, X., & Tan, F. (2012b). Improved bioavailability of poorly water-soluble
612 drug curcumin in cellulose acetate solid dispersion. *AAPS PharmSciTech*, 13(1), 159–

613 166. <https://doi.org/10.1208/s12249-011-9732-9>

614 Wang, L., Yang, H., Hou, J., Zhang, W., Xiang, C., & Li, L. (2017). Effect of the electrical
615 conductivity of core solutions on the morphology and structure of core-shell CA-
616 PCL/CS nanofibers. *New Journal of Chemistry*, 41(24), 15072–15078.
617 <https://doi.org/10.1039/c7nj02805a>

618 Yam, K. L., & Zhu, X. (2012). Controlled release food and beverage packaging. *Emerging*
619 *Food Packaging Technologies*, 13–26. <https://doi.org/10.1533/9780857095664.1.13>

620 Yang, X., Zhu, B., Dong, T., Pan, P., Shuai, X., & Inoue, Y. (2008). Interactions between an
621 anticancer drug and polymeric micelles based on biodegradable polyesters.
622 *Macromolecular Bioscience*, 8(12), 1116–1125.
623 <https://doi.org/10.1002/mabi.200800085>

624 Yang, Y., Li, W., Yu, D. G., Wang, G., Williams, G. R., & Zhang, Z. (2019). Tunable drug
625 release from nanofibers coated with blank cellulose acetate layers fabricated using tri-
626 axial electrospinning. *Carbohydrate Polymers*, 203, 228–237.
627 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbpol.2018.09.061>

628 Zou, Y., Zhang, C., Wang, P., Zhang, Y., & Zhang, H. (2020). Electrospun
629 chitosan/polycaprolactone nanofibers containing chlorogenic acid-loaded halloysite
630 nanotube for active food packaging. *Carbohydrate Polymers*, 247, 116711.
631 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbpol.2020.116711>

632